

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Supplementary Information for: Trait-based paleontological niche prediction recovers extinct ecological breadth of the earliest specialized ant predators

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Methods – Homologous versus functional morphology of hell ants

Most hell ant traits were distinguished as homologous to extant species; however, because haidomyrmecine cranial morphology is highly modified, eye position is difficult to assess in the context of modern ant variation. Extant ants (and most extinct ants, including the Dominican *Pseudomyrmex* fossil) have a prognathous head posture, in which the long axis of the head is held parallel to the ground with the oral opening pointing anteriorly. In many other insect taxa, such as wasps and grasshoppers, the head is held in a hypognathous posture; the long axis of the head is held perpendicular to the ground, with the oral opening positioned ventrally. A hypognathous-like head posture is also present in hell ants, a configuration not seen in any extant ant. This difference in head posture means that, interpreted strictly on the basis of homology, the dorsoventral axis of the extant ant head is the anteroposterior axis of the hell ant head, and vice versa; that eye positioning along each axis is similarly swapped. When interpreted this way, the eye position of the hell ant is more similar to many *Camponotus* species: positioned extremely posteriorly and more dorsally.

Functionally, however, the hell ant would have been moving with its head held hypognathously, as evidenced by fossilized posture as well as preserved predation (Perrichot et al 2008; Barden & Grimaldi 2012; Perrichot et al. 2016; Barden et al. 2020) thus the functional anteroposterior axis of the hell ant head would be from its clypeal protrusion or horn to the occipital foramen, rather than the homologous anteroposterior axis of the head running perpendicular to the ground from vertex to oral opening. Considering that our question is a question of functional ecology - what is the ecological occupation of hell ants? - we measured traits related to eye position both functionally and homologically, to incorporate this possible variation (Figures S1, S2).

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Figure S1.

Eye positioning measurements consistent with homologous morphology.

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Figure S2.

Eye positioning measurements consistent with functional morphology.

Figure S3.

Principal component analysis of extant and extinct morphospace using raw trait measurements. The morphospace of each lineage with an independent origin of trap-jaw mechanics is delineated.

Figure S4. Principal component analysis of extant and extinct morphospace using shape ratio measurements. The morphospace of each lineage with an independent origin of trap-jaw mechanics is delineated.

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Figure S5.

Principal component analysis of extant and extinct morphospace using log-shape variable measurements. The morphospace of each lineage with an independent origin of trap-jaw mechanics is delineated.

Figure S6.

Variable importance plots for each Random Forest classification model (foraging niche; functional role; nesting niche; ecomorph syndrome) using linear trait measurement data. Variable importance is calculated as the mean decrease in accuracy across splits when the variable was eliminated; a higher decrease in accuracy when that variable was omitted indicates greater importance to the model.

Figure S7.

Variable importance plots for each Random Forest classification model (foraging niche; functional role; nesting niche; ecomorph syndrome) using shape ratio measurement data. Variable importance is calculated as the mean decrease in accuracy across splits when the variable was eliminated; a higher decrease in accuracy when that variable was omitted indicates greater importance to the model.

Figure S8.

Variable importance plots for each Random Forest classification model (foraging niche; functional role; nesting niche; ecomorph syndrome) using log-shape variable measurement data. Variable importance is calculated as the mean decrease in accuracy across splits when the variable was eliminated; a higher decrease in accuracy when that variable was omitted indicates greater importance to the model.

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Trait	Formula	Interpretation
Head shape (HS)	HW/HL	Larger value = more boxy, square head Smaller value = more elongate along anteroposterior axis
Procoxal proportion (PP)	PL/WL	Larger value = procoxa longer in comparison to body length Smaller value = procoxa shorter in comparison to body length
Eye proportion (EP)	EL/HL	Larger value = eyes large in comparison to head Smaller value = eyes small in comparison to head
Pronotum expansion (PE)	PW/WL	Larger value = pronotum laterally expanded in relation to body size Smaller value = pronotum laterally narrow in relation to body size
Pronotum flattening (PF)	PW/MH	Larger value = pronotum broad and dorsoventrally flattened Smaller value = pronotum narrow and dorsoventrally expanded
Mesosoma shape (MS)	MH/WL	Larger value = overall elongate narrow body Smaller value = overall stocky squarish body
Mandible curvature (MC)	MLP/MLF	Larger value = low degree of mandible curvature Smaller value = high degree of mandible curvature
Mandible proportion (MP)	MLP/HL	Larger value = elongate mandibles in comparison with head size Smaller value = short mandibles in comparison with head size
Dorsoventral eye position (DEP)	EHD/HH	Larger value = eye positioned more ventrally Smaller value = eye positioned more dorsally
Anteroposterior eye position (AEP)	ELA/LHL	Larger value = eye positioned more posteriorly Smaller value = eye positioned more anteriorly
Scape proportion (SP)	SL/HL	Larger value = scape elongate in comparison with head size Smaller value = scape short in comparison with head size
Metafemur proportion (MeP)	ML/WL	Larger value = elongate leg in relation to body size Smaller value = shorter leg in relation to body size

Table S1.

Shape ratios of traits measured, formulae for calculation, and interpretation of ratio value.

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Ecomorph designation based on granular binnings	Functional role binnings collapsed	Final ecomorph syndromes
fg_gr_eg	om_gr_eg	<p>Ground or leaf litter-nesting epigaeic omnivore om_grll_eg Exemplars: <i>Camponotus</i>; <i>Dinoponera</i>; <i>Aphaenogaster</i></p>
gn_gr_eg		
mh_gr_ll		
om_gr_eg		
om_gr_ab		
om_gr_ll		
om_ll_eg		
gn_leaf	om_leaf	<p>Leaf litter omnivore om_leaf Exemplars: <i>Aneuretus</i>; <i>Acanthomyrmex</i>; <i>Cyphomyrmex</i></p>
om_leaf		
om_lg_ab	om_lg_ab	<p>Lignicolous arboreal omnivore om_lg_ab Exemplars: <i>Pseudomyrmex</i>; <i>Cataulacus</i>; <i>Cephalotes</i></p>
py_lg_ab		
tr_lg_ab		
om_cn_ab	om_cn_ab	<p>Carton-nesting arboreal omnivore om_cn_ab Exemplars: <i>Crematogaster</i>; <i>Oceophylla</i>; <i>Azteca</i></p>
om_cn_eg	om_cn_eg	
om_sub	om_sub	<p>Subterranean omnivore om_sub Exemplars: <i>Acropyga</i></p>
gp_gr_eg	pred_gr_eg	<p>Ground-nesting epigaeic or leaf litter predator pred_gr_egll Exemplars: <i>Odontomachus</i>; <i>Diacamma</i>; <i>Harpegnathos</i></p>
sp_gr_eg	pred_gr_ll	
gp_gr_ll		
gp_leaf	pred_leaf	<p>Leaf litter predator pred_leaf Exemplars: <i>Hypoponera</i>; <i>Mystrium</i>; <i>Strumigenys</i></p>
sp_leaf		
sp_lg_ab	pred_lg_ab	<p>Lignicolous arboreal predator pred_lg_ab Exemplars: <i>Simopone</i>; <i>Cylindromyrmex</i>; <i>Daceton</i></p>
gp_lg_ab		
gp_ll_cr	pred_ll_cr	<p>Column-raiding predator pred_cr Exemplars: <i>Simopelta</i>; <i>Neivamyrmex</i>; <i>Cheliomyrmex</i></p>
gp_sb_cr	pred_sb_cr	
sp_sb_cr		

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sp_gr_cr	pred_gr_cr	
gp_ll_eg	pred_ll_eg	Leaf litter-nesting epigeaic predator pred_ll_eg Exemplars: <i>Leptogenys</i> ; <i>Platythyrea</i>
sp_ll_eg		
gp_sb_ll	pred_sb_ll	Subterranean predator pred_sub Exemplars: <i>Proceratium</i> ; <i>Stigmatomma</i> ; <i>Leptanilla</i>
sp_sb_ll		

Table S2.

Schematic of ecomorph syndrome collapse: ecomorphs were collapsed based on ecological and morphological overlap between groups, and qualitative assessment of likely ecological overlap (leaf litter foragers may also forage on the surface of the ground, for example). Final column shows ecomorph syndrome abbreviations, definitions, and exemplar taxa (abbreviations used in raw dataset available on Dryad (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.kh1893243>)).

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Species	Specimen accession number	Caste	Sampling method
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	BALTJ_025	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	BALTJ_016	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	BALTJ_027	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	BALTJ_029	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	BALTJ_043	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	BALTJ_050	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	BALTJ_031	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	BALTJ_030	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	BALTJ_059	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	BALTJ_056	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	BALTJ_022	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	BALTJ_017	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	BALTJ_009	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	BALTJ_066	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	BALTJ_007	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	BALTJ_004	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	BALTJ_011	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	BALTJ_003	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	BALTJ_010	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	BALTJ_065	Worker	Measured under light microscopy
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	BuPH-1	Worker	Measured from micro-CT reconstruction
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	Bu-FB80	Dealate queen	Measured from micro-CT reconstruction
<i>Pseudomyrmex c.f. macrops</i>	DR-14-1021	Worker	Measured from micro-CT reconstruction
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	IGR.BU-003	Alate queen	Measured under light microscopy

Table S3.

List of all fossil specimens included in the study, with caste and measurement type information included. All specimens with accession numbers beginning in BALTJ are from a private collection, while specimens with alternate accession numbers are housed at the American Museum of Natural History (*Linguamyrmex vladi* and *Haidomyrmex scimitarus*); the New Jersey Institute of Technology (*Pseudomyrmex macrops*); and at the University of Rennes (*Dhagnathos autokrator*).

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0322	0.502	0.0182	0.35	0.0976	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.136	0.3546	0.0466	0.3012	0.1616	Gr
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0892	0.0846	0.7778	0.0416	0.0068	Lg
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0424	0.6124	0.0658	0.1712	0.1082	Gr

Table S4.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, linear trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	Ll	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.075	0.1058	0.4062	0.413	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.2614	0.1728	0.3334	0.2324	Eg
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.9048	0.0074	0.0322	0.0556	Ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.2752	0.1276	0.43	0.1672	Eg

Table S5.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, linear trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.2072	0.1658	0.3222	0.1426	0.0072	0.155	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0994	0.0576	0.304	0.277	0.0062	0.2558	GP
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.018	0	0.2766	0.2616	0.3034	0.1404	Py
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.043	0.0496	0.1808	0.232	0.0114	0.4832	SP

Table S6.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, linear trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_le_af	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0416	0.4052	0.085	0.0102	0.0718	0.0836	0.2484	0.0122	0.0352	0.0068	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.096	0.338	0.015	0.01	0.0656	0.1426	0.1952	0.013	0.1214	0.0032	om_grll_eg
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.159	0.054	0.0154	0.4104	0.0104	0.0078	0.048	0.287	6.00E-04	0.0074	om_lg_ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0144	0.248	0	0.0102	0.0178	0.4646	0.1218	0.1052	0.0174	0	pred_gr_egll

Table S7.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, linear trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0232	0.1886	0.03	0.5856	0.1726	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.039	0.4696	0.0574	0.2966	0.1374	Gr
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0924	0.084	0.7782	0.04	0.0054	Lg
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0088	0.68	0.0474	0.1728	0.091	Gr

Table S8.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, linear trait measurements, homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	LI	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0528	0.158	0.3324	0.4568	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.2258	0.1488	0.334	0.2914	Eg
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.9014	0.0084	0.0304	0.0598	Ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.2124	0.1082	0.4696	0.2098	Eg

Table S9.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, linear trait measurements, homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.055	0.1854	0.3942	0.1782	0.0268	0.1604	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.019	0.0436	0.2066	0.3202	0.0476	0.363	SP
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0188	2.00E-04	0.2766	0.2478	0.313	0.1436	Py
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0248	0.0418	0.0614	0.2192	0.0254	0.6274	SP

Table S10.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, linear trait measurements, homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_le_af	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0308	0.3514	0.0834	0.0508	0.116	0.0496	0.283	0.0048	0.0244	0.0058	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0216	0.3756	0.0134	0.0598	0.0558	0.112	0.2732	0.0128	0.0708	0.005	om_grll_eg
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.1624	0.0568	0.0116	0.4136	0.0142	0.0092	0.0456	0.279	2.00E-04	0.0074	om_lg_ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0048	0.2558	0	0.0328	0.0202	0.475	0.1918	0.0134	0.0052	0	pred_gr_egll

Table S11.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, linear trait measurements, homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.049	0.6252	0.0074	0.2694	0.049	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0266	0.5414	0.0972	0.2838	0.051	Gr
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0086	0.0686	0.843	0.0678	0.012	Lg
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0184	0.4248	0.0814	0.42	0.0554	Gr

Table S12.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	Ll	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.1572	0.062	0.6564	0.1244	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.2086	0.108	0.4724	0.211	Eg
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.8186	0.0142	0.1376	0.0296	Ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.1462	0.067	0.3526	0.4342	Ll

Table S13.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.037	0.0328	0.3172	0.362	8.00E-04	0.2502	Om
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0074	0.02	0.4008	0.1708	0.0202	0.3808	GP
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	8.00E-04	0.0044	0.0866	0.051	0.7116	0.1456	Py
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0458	0.0158	0.383	0.1612	0.0322	0.362	GP

Table S14.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_le_af	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0684	0.2738	0.0552	6.00E-04	0.0558	0.4122	0.1088	0.0058	0.0192	2.00E-04	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0114	0.1738	0.0102	0.0146	0.0308	0.4666	0.1072	0.0624	0.1136	0.0094	pred_gr_egll
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0066	0.0354	0.0048	0.6404	0.0072	0.0222	0.0098	0.231	0.0406	0.002	om_lg_ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0136	0.1948	0.025	0.0136	0.0216	0.2822	0.3438	0.0352	0.059	0.0112	pred_leaf

Table S15.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0366	0.674	0.0064	0.2228	0.0602	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0206	0.6094	0.0786	0.234	0.0574	Gr
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0138	0.0708	0.8422	0.0638	0.0094	Lg
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0202	0.2926	0.1466	0.485	0.0556	Ll

Table S16.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, shape ratio trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	Ll	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.1468	0.0678	0.6546	0.1308	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.1956	0.1006	0.509	0.1948	Eg
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.8224	0.0124	0.1394	0.0258	Ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.1982	0.062	0.261	0.4788	Ll

Table S17.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, shape ratio trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0276	0.0546	0.2514	0.3588	0.001	0.3066	Om
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.003	0.0196	0.2828	0.1952	0.037	0.4624	SP
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0	0.005	0.0872	0.0454	0.6976	0.1648	Py
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0114	0.017	0.2314	0.1764	0.046	0.5178	SP

Table S18.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, shape ratio trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_le_af	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.05	0.303	0.0564	2.00E-04	0.0574	0.4042	0.1094	0.0082	0.011	2.00E-04	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0058	0.2034	0.0114	0.0124	0.0298	0.5468	0.091	0.0528	0.0294	0.0172	pred_gr_egll
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0062	0.04	0.003	0.6426	0.0074	0.0238	0.0102	0.2282	0.0372	0.0014	om_lg_ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0156	0.1462	0.0214	0.0344	0.0212	0.1492	0.4522	0.1158	0.0172	0.0268	pred_leaf

Table S19.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, shape ratio trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.033	0.3944	0.0242	0.4636	0.0848	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0164	0.3428	0.1238	0.4516	0.0654	Ll
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0214	0.0716	0.8258	0.0712	0.01	Lg
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0202	0.3486	0.0812	0.488	0.062	Ll

Table S20.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, log-shape variable measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	Ll	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0954	0.0816	0.4652	0.3578	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.1636	0.1528	0.3204	0.3632	Ll
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.8032	0.024	0.112	0.0608	Ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.1284	0.0824	0.2326	0.5566	Ll

Table S21.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, log-shape variable measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0526	0.0516	0.3292	0.3226	0.0034	0.2406	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.011	0.0138	0.4252	0.1884	0.0314	0.3302	SP
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	4.00E-04	0.0042	0.0998	0.0572	0.7034	0.135	Py
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.041	0.0124	0.3924	0.1872	0.031	0.336	GP

Table S22.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, log-shape variable measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_e_gll	pred_le_af	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0692	0.2434	0.1376	0.0034	0.0574	0.247	0.2016	0.0224	0.0174	6.00E-04	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0158	0.184	0.0396	0.0274	0.0394	0.22	0.2782	0.096	0.0882	0.0114	pred_leaf
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0138	0.0518	0.0072	0.6466	0.0082	0.0104	0.025	0.2114	0.0238	0.0018	om_lg_ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0198	0.1836	0.0484	0.0204	0.0262	0.157	0.4384	0.055	0.0412	0.01	pred_leaf

Table S23.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, log-shape variable measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0302	0.3864	0.0254	0.4378	0.1202	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0142	0.3404	0.1008	0.4436	0.101	Ll
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.021	0.089	0.8096	0.069	0.0114	Lg
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0194	0.1982	0.1256	0.5806	0.0762	Ll

Table S24.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, log-shape variable measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	Ll	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0966	0.1034	0.4488	0.3512	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.151	0.1666	0.3178	0.3646	Ll
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.8098	0.022	0.1072	0.061	Ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.1552	0.0962	0.1778	0.5708	Ll

Table S25.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, log-shape variable measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0416	0.0556	0.2538	0.346	0.0014	0.3016	Om
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0058	0.018	0.3232	0.2082	0.0364	0.4084	SP
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	6.00E-04	0.007	0.0938	0.0638	0.6954	0.1394	Py
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0144	0.0166	0.2528	0.1814	0.0472	0.4876	SP

Table S26.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, log-shape variable measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_le_af	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Linguamyrmex vladi</i>	0.0486	0.2668	0.1392	0.0044	0.0634	0.2518	0.1924	0.0168	0.0126	0.004	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0104	0.2208	0.0362	0.0306	0.0522	0.2444	0.268	0.0764	0.0426	0.0184	pred_gr_egll
<i>Pseudomyrmex macrops</i>	0.0114	0.0492	0.0068	0.6548	0.0106	0.0108	0.0258	0.2054	0.024	0.0012	om_lg_ab
<i>Dhagnathos autokrator</i>	0.0236	0.1238	0.033	0.0284	0.025	0.0812	0.5186	0.1332	0.0132	0.02	pred_leaf

Table S27.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on full morphometric dataset, log-shape variable measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0598	0.3838	0.0762	0.4338	0.0464	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.057	0.485	0.0416	0.2394	0.177	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0382	0.4644	0.1014	0.3522	0.0438	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0736	0.519	0.0402	0.2826	0.0846	Gr
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0762	0.5304	0.0466	0.2896	0.0572	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0912	0.6572	0.0166	0.202	0.033	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0646	0.5374	0.0234	0.2556	0.119	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.0552	0.5154	0.0342	0.36	0.0352	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0572	0.4372	0.0872	0.3666	0.0518	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0662	0.4752	0.0368	0.2536	0.1682	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0508	0.3036	0.2456	0.3598	0.0402	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0426	0.355	0.1906	0.361	0.0508	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0352	0.3664	0.2152	0.3422	0.041	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0468	0.3816	0.1986	0.3056	0.0674	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0376	0.3426	0.2926	0.2666	0.0606	Cn
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0806	0.442	0.0288	0.249	0.1996	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0412	0.4184	0.1834	0.2888	0.0682	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0752	0.4584	0.0474	0.2482	0.1708	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0294	0.3846	0.1996	0.3448	0.0416	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0192	0.2474	0.2866	0.3914	0.0554	Ll

Table S28.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; linear trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	Ll	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0986	0.0744	0.2564	0.5706	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1966	0.1784	0.384	0.241	Eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.172	0.0578	0.2922	0.478	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.13	0.0842	0.4284	0.3574	Eg
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.1536	0.089	0.4234	0.334	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.252	0.019	0.653	0.076	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.238	0.0954	0.512	0.1546	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.1	0.0648	0.3994	0.4358	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.1608	0.0972	0.3546	0.3874	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.2018	0.1692	0.425	0.204	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.3014	0.0798	0.1928	0.426	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2274	0.0466	0.2878	0.4382	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2136	0.076	0.3052	0.4052	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2506	0.0792	0.2868	0.3834	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2774	0.0734	0.2738	0.3754	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.2156	0.1968	0.3992	0.1884	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2306	0.1016	0.2492	0.4186	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.216	0.2006	0.4204	0.163	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.2432	0.1048	0.2476	0.4044	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.2582	0.0602	0.2704	0.4112	Ll

Table S29.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; linear trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.1016	0.0506	0.1618	0.253	0.0566	0.3764	SP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1676	0.0496	0.2944	0.2472	0.014	0.2272	GP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1592	0.0742	0.3004	0.1192	0.0364	0.3106	SP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.2452	0.0546	0.2304	0.152	0.0104	0.3074	SP
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.3096	0.08	0.0948	0.2104	0.0666	0.2386	Fg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.1842	0.055	0.1616	0.3338	0.0028	0.2626	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.1486	0.0734	0.2288	0.268	0.0068	0.2744	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.229	0.1706	0.135	0.1818	0.0452	0.2384	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.1612	0.0706	0.3864	0.161	0.0234	0.1974	GP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.1314	0.0716	0.2904	0.2572	0.0114	0.238	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.11	0.042	0.151	0.1024	0.1224	0.4722	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1528	0.047	0.2392	0.1324	0.0618	0.3668	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1302	0.0378	0.2434	0.1506	0.0624	0.3756	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1756	0.06	0.1452	0.1302	0.0696	0.4194	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2224	0.0808	0.1288	0.101	0.0666	0.4004	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.108	0.0286	0.2866	0.3028	0.0176	0.2564	Om
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1756	0.0372	0.187	0.1384	0.0416	0.4202	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.1548	0.0384	0.275	0.278	0.0132	0.2406	Om
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.208	0.0376	0.2088	0.1938	0.0544	0.2974	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.113	0.075	0.1456	0.0944	0.0948	0.4772	SP

Table S30.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; linear trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_l_eaf	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0578	0.2526	0.158	0.0544	0.075 4	0.064	0.2268	0.0848	0.0038	0.0224	om_grll_eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0656	0.3268	0.010 8	0.0118	0.056 4	0.1744	0.2716	0.017	0.0654	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0436	0.2244	0.076 2	0.0712	0.044 4	0.0384	0.4158	0.0436	0.0324	0.01	pred_leaf
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0506	0.2992	0.026 4	0.026	0.046 2	0.0866	0.3874	0.012	0.0626	0.003	pred_leaf
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.1194	0.405	0.108	0.0892	0.071 8	0.028	0.111	0.0174	0.0446	0.0056	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0838	0.396	0.002 8	0.0014	0.012	0.2324	0.1946	0.017	0.0598	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0814	0.3842	0.003 4	0.0026	0.023 6	0.1794	0.2432	0.0106	0.0714	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.0716	0.4046	0.201 2	0.065	0.037 8	0.0432	0.138	0.0076	0.0254	0.0056	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0468	0.2786	0.031 2	0.0276	0.064	0.0502	0.4588	0.0112	0.0298	0.0018	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.079	0.3368	0.008	0.0062	0.043	0.2066	0.234	0.0132	0.073	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.1102	0.1584	0.075 8	0.1518	0.039 4	0.0286	0.2254	0.189	0.0086	0.0128	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0472	0.1746	0.056 2	0.1264	0.041 6	0.0444	0.3034	0.1356	0.0572	0.0134	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0438	0.207	0.044	0.1276	0.071	0.0358	0.2872	0.1122	0.0628	0.0086	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.06	0.1958	0.053 8	0.1508	0.064 6	0.0372	0.2004	0.147	0.0746	0.0158	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0418	0.2396	0.042 6	0.1212	0.054 2	0.0428	0.209	0.1694	0.0548	0.0246	om_grll_eg

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.082	0.3636	0.0036	0.0108	0.0596	0.2104	0.1606	0.0096	0.0998	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0688	0.2302	0.091	0.0952	0.0628	0.0496	0.176	0.1854	0.0224	0.0186	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0898	0.3548	0.0016	0.0156	0.0662	0.2046	0.1214	0.011	0.1344	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0544	0.2744	0.106	0.109	0.053	0.0436	0.1388	0.1768	0.0294	0.0146	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0358	0.2108	0.0304	0.162	0.0486	0.0794	0.1852	0.1034	0.125	0.0194	om_grll_eg

Table S31.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; linear trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0384	0.2442	0.0898	0.5854	0.0422	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0074	0.4942	0.0608	0.2844	0.1532	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0574	0.1966	0.1402	0.507	0.0988	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.034	0.2198	0.0466	0.5722	0.1274	Ll
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.033	0.2098	0.0432	0.6314	0.0826	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0084	0.8596	0.0304	0.0828	0.0188	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0058	0.6526	0.046	0.1858	0.1098	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.0482	0.1406	0.0376	0.708	0.0656	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.019	0.184	0.1028	0.6352	0.059	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0088	0.577	0.0556	0.2204	0.1382	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0662	0.2	0.2552	0.4328	0.0458	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.043	0.3078	0.2038	0.401	0.0444	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0374	0.1636	0.2776	0.4484	0.073	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0424	0.1274	0.234	0.5152	0.081	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0202	0.1118	0.2906	0.4878	0.0896	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0134	0.5824	0.0606	0.214	0.1296	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.062	0.1338	0.223	0.4516	0.1296	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0292	0.5052	0.079	0.2054	0.1812	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0266	0.3602	0.2272	0.3438	0.0422	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0136	0.2024	0.2682	0.446	0.0698	Ll

Table S32.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; linear trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	LI	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0864	0.0914	0.1778	0.6444	LI
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0928	0.1676	0.4108	0.3288	Eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1808	0.075	0.2518	0.4924	LI
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0866	0.1364	0.3178	0.4592	LI
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0776	0.102	0.3904	0.43	LI
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.1526	0.0194	0.7488	0.0792	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.1634	0.1106	0.5472	0.1788	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.0778	0.0826	0.2944	0.5452	LI
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.065	0.1212	0.2836	0.5302	LI
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.1474	0.1606	0.4448	0.2472	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.3078	0.0824	0.1786	0.4312	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.217	0.0488	0.3048	0.4294	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2186	0.0836	0.2414	0.4564	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.232	0.059	0.263	0.446	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.232	0.1114	0.2186	0.438	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.2052	0.13	0.414	0.2508	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2532	0.0988	0.171	0.477	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.1976	0.1906	0.4222	0.1896	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.2514	0.085	0.2622	0.4014	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.208	0.0832	0.258	0.4508	LI

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Table S33.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; linear trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0998	0.0466	0.1796	0.1574	0.0518	0.4648	SP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0318	0.061	0.3106	0.2362	0.08	0.2804	GP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0848	0.1064	0.322	0.1258	0.0582	0.3028	GP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.046	0.0978	0.3204	0.2192	0.037	0.2796	GP
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0794	0.0954	0.216	0.289	0.067	0.2532	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0396	0.0306	0.1186	0.4328	0.0542	0.3242	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0216	0.0636	0.1878	0.3358	0.0732	0.318	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.0844	0.1938	0.194	0.2334	0.0452	0.2492	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0386	0.1178	0.3982	0.1722	0.0582	0.215	GP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0234	0.055	0.2526	0.3058	0.081	0.2822	Om
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.057	0.0388	0.1812	0.1338	0.1736	0.4156	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1042	0.0644	0.2236	0.1662	0.0912	0.3504	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0878	0.0904	0.2576	0.1102	0.1004	0.3536	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0544	0.0852	0.195	0.1636	0.0974	0.4044	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0322	0.0854	0.2618	0.1664	0.085	0.3692	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0564	0.0386	0.1404	0.3496	0.0724	0.3426	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0554	0.0408	0.2708	0.1428	0.0882	0.402	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.044	0.0378	0.1976	0.3738	0.0844	0.2624	Om
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.1206	0.0274	0.2576	0.1944	0.1068	0.2932	SP

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0356	0.113	0.2284	0.1366	0.0994	0.387	SP
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Table S34.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; linear trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_l_eaf	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0424	0.135	0.219	0.0462	0.0718	0.1054	0.2652	0.093	0.0024	0.0196	pred_leaf
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0082	0.2986	0.0144	0.0644	0.0508	0.1856	0.3356	0.0094	0.0322	0	pred_leaf
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0492	0.1868	0.0918	0.0972	0.0586	0.0274	0.4056	0.0386	0.0272	0.0176	pred_leaf
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0366	0.2668	0.0392	0.052	0.0848	0.0512	0.409	0.0092	0.0462	0.005	pred_leaf
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0812	0.4286	0.0738	0.0708	0.105	0.0378	0.1346	0.0224	0.0384	0.0074	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0114	0.4306	0.0036	0.0464	0.016	0.2274	0.224	0.0142	0.026	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0122	0.3858	0.0062	0.051	0.0414	0.1664	0.2982	0.0082	0.0302	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.0688	0.373	0.1954	0.0668	0.0672	0.0338	0.1634	0.0052	0.0162	0.0102	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.019	0.1966	0.0568	0.065	0.089	0.0274	0.517	0.0056	0.0182	0.0054	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0102	0.3314	0.0094	0.0618	0.0484	0.199	0.295	0.011	0.0332	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.1096	0.167	0.0658	0.1542	0.0406	0.0172	0.2366	0.1888	0.0072	0.013	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0464	0.212	0.0738	0.1242	0.0378	0.0362	0.2596	0.1398	0.0498	0.0204	pred_leaf

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0406	0.163	0.083 6	0.1436	0.083 2	0.0212	0.2748	0.1196	0.0544	0.016	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.057	0.2198	0.048 6	0.1436	0.068 2	0.0162	0.2008	0.1536	0.067	0.0252	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0332	0.19	0.044	0.1394	0.113 2	0.014	0.2506	0.1464	0.0426	0.0266	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0154	0.3938	0.008	0.0652	0.040 6	0.2328	0.1854	0.009	0.0492	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0706	0.1688	0.065 2	0.1158	0.092 8	0.0496	0.198	0.1944	0.0238	0.021	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0254	0.4188	0.004 2	0.0784	0.072 8	0.1626	0.163	0.011	0.0628	0.001	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.043	0.2726	0.074 4	0.1262	0.042 2	0.0516	0.1436	0.213	0.022	0.0114	om_grll_eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0324	0.1804	0.048 8	0.1762	0.103 8	0.0574	0.1936	0.0774	0.1062	0.0238	pred_leaf

Table S35.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; linear trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0684	0.6814	0.0074	0.2158	0.027	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0424	0.7562	6.00E-04	0.1998	0.001	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0482	0.704	0.0018	0.2322	0.0138	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0326	0.7176	0.023	0.2146	0.0122	Gr
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0256	0.6942	0.0226	0.242	0.0156	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0252	0.6544	0.002	0.3162	0.0022	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0212	0.6548	0.0044	0.3188	0	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.2636	0.2216	0.0608	0.4474	0.0066	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0634	0.6044	0.0108	0.3094	0.012	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0434	0.7008	0.0024	0.239	0.0144	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0206	0.1626	0.5006	0.2918	0.0244	Lg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.004	0.548	0.0458	0.4	0.0022	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0116	0.8092	0.0194	0.1556	0.0042	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0022	0.743	0.0856	0.1658	0.0034	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0304	0.3702	0.258	0.32	0.0214	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.055	0.7134	0.0088	0.2052	0.0176	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0026	0.5238	0.2264	0.2288	0.0184	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0066	0.707	0.0744	0.2032	0.0088	Gr

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0022	0.7738	0.0692	0.1506	0.0042	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.003	0.5718	0.1326	0.2886	0.004	Gr

Table S36.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; functional morphology.

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	LI	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.1752	0.0844	0.5354	0.205	Eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1584	0.0032	0.59	0.2484	Eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1658	0.0132	0.5646	0.2564	Eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.11	0.0826	0.5422	0.2652	Eg
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.2024	0.0676	0.6052	0.1248	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.1838	0.0022	0.4504	0.3636	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.1978	0.002	0.5542	0.246	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.403	0.0424	0.2646	0.29	Ab
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.2446	0.0182	0.502	0.2352	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.2264	0.0142	0.4928	0.2666	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.3572	0.2008	0.2432	0.1988	Ab
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1086	0.0674	0.5246	0.2994	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1166	0.0642	0.6328	0.1864	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1594	0.0844	0.5338	0.2224	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2292	0.162	0.4284	0.1804	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.165	0.0598	0.5762	0.199	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1918	0.0992	0.4758	0.2332	Eg

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.1104	0.0872	0.584	0.2184	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0934	0.057	0.6406	0.209	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.1078	0.0872	0.5662	0.2388	Eg

Table S37.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; functional morphology.

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0434	0.1026	0.1652	0.4172	2.00E-04	0.2714	Om
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1128	0.0178	0.5196	0.2742	0	0.075	GP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0924	0.0332	0.4498	0.283	0.001	0.1406	GP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.066	0.0764	0.4536	0.2248	0.0022	0.177	GP
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0106	0.0128	0.1504	0.2706	0.001	0.5546	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0942	0.0364	0.3288	0.4298	0	0.1106	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0596	0.0104	0.2864	0.4004	0	0.243	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.0314	0.024	0.1766	0.3368	0.0014	0.4298	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.1124	0.0122	0.336	0.34	0	0.1994	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0606	0.0218	0.4288	0.331	0	0.1578	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.009	8.00E-04	0.3848	0.101	0.0618	0.4426	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0032	0.0014	0.6024	0.1608	0.0156	0.2166	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0036	2.00E-04	0.7118	0.1194	0.0092	0.1558	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0038	0.0296	0.5182	0.1168	0.0202	0.3114	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0934	0.0184	0.4184	0.1162	0.0288	0.3248	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0352	0.0128	0.428	0.2884	0.0012	0.2344	GP

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0064	0.0106	0.3556	0.094	0.0446	0.4888	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.003	0.035	0.522	0.1148	0.0182	0.307	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.002	0.0092	0.6058	0.0974	0.0182	0.2674	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0038	0.0374	0.2948	0.1204	0.0324	0.5112	SP

Table S38.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; functional morphology.

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_l_eaf	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.055	0.328	0.110 2	0	0.029 2	0.3218	0.1372	0.0062	0.0116	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.063	0.2064	0.046 6	0	0.002 8	0.5138	0.1148	0	0.0522	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.059	0.216	0.060 6	0	0.014 2	0.3868	0.2192	0.001	0.0428	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.02	0.2284	0.027 2	0.0028	0.02	0.549	0.1062	0.009	0.0364	0.001	pred_gr_egll
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0142	0.2096	0.004	0.0026	0.014 6	0.5278	0.0854	0.0326	0.1084	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0452	0.3486	0.061	0	0.001 2	0.238	0.272	0.0036	0.0304	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0426	0.2928	0.030 6	0	0.001	0.32	0.2546	0.0018	0.0566	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.1488	0.1564	0.017 2	0.0018	0.019 6	0.2324	0.3284	0.0674	0.0274	0	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0688	0.2716	0.032	0	0.013 6	0.3018	0.2594	0.0064	0.0456	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0508	0.2064	0.032 6	0	0.011	0.3674	0.283	0.001	0.0472	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0154	0.0296	0.001	0.088	0.024	0.147	0.1572	0.4262	0.1048	0.0068	pred_lg_ab

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0038	0.1488	0.003 4	0.0074	0.004 6	0.5314	0.1946	0.0162	0.0892	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0078	0.0982	0.001 2	0.003	0.006	0.6876	0.0702	0.0122	0.1134	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0016	0.1446	0.002	0.0246	0.007 6	0.5886	0.1084	0.044	0.0768	0.0018	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0298	0.111	0.022 2	0.0962	0.043 4	0.2588	0.1262	0.1654	0.141	0.006	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0334	0.1938	0.017 2	0.0014	0.02	0.4756	0.208	0.0042	0.046	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.002	0.0712	0	0.1434	0.008 6	0.3544	0.1126	0.1754	0.1244	0.008	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0062	0.1108	0.001	0.0096	0.022	0.6138	0.0988	0.0278	0.109	0.001	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0014	0.084	0	0.0096	0.011 8	0.7518	0.084	0.0246	0.0304	0.0022	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.002	0.095	0.003 6	0.0882	0.015 6	0.431	0.1304	0.1152	0.1168	0.0022	pred_gr_egll

Table S39.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0392	0.5364	0.0298	0.3762	0.0184	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0236	0.8092	0.0024	0.1628	0.002	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.024	0.7864	0.0026	0.176	0.011	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0238	0.6812	0.0424	0.2208	0.0318	Gr
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0202	0.7678	0.0176	0.1806	0.0138	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0102	0.7622	0.002	0.2246	0.001	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0062	0.7626	0.0038	0.2252	0.0022	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.2566	0.2498	0.0588	0.4286	0.0062	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.048	0.6416	0.0176	0.2768	0.016	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0272	0.7662	0.0028	0.187	0.0168	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.013	0.1366	0.5272	0.2864	0.0368	Lg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0052	0.4744	0.0716	0.4432	0.0056	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0084	0.7316	0.0324	0.2228	0.0048	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.004	0.655	0.1158	0.202	0.0232	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0328	0.2728	0.3176	0.341	0.0358	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0308	0.7934	0.01	0.1502	0.0156	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0024	0.4766	0.2318	0.2524	0.0368	Gr

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.008	0.6384	0.094	0.2388	0.0208	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0034	0.6742	0.0928	0.2118	0.0178	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0022	0.5782	0.149	0.2532	0.0174	Gr

Table S40.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	LI	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.099	0.0394	0.5154	0.3462	Eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.151	0.004	0.6054	0.2396	Eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0936	0.01	0.6584	0.238	Eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1374	0.0996	0.5312	0.2318	Eg
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.1694	0.0638	0.6568	0.11	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.1136	0.0012	0.5652	0.32	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.1068	0.0036	0.6584	0.2312	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.3652	0.0286	0.3038	0.3024	Ab
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.177	0.0234	0.5522	0.2474	Eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.2352	0.014	0.5354	0.2154	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.4392	0.183	0.1976	0.1802	Ab
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1836	0.0676	0.4668	0.282	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1196	0.0638	0.611	0.2056	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2378	0.079	0.4984	0.1848	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.31	0.2054	0.3108	0.1738	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0926	0.0464	0.6744	0.1866	Eg

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2252	0.0598	0.4966	0.2184	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.1356	0.0852	0.5698	0.2094	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.1418	0.0776	0.5776	0.203	Eg
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.1302	0.0806	0.5828	0.2064	Eg

Table S41.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0398	0.1744	0.1106	0.2534	0.0066	0.4152	SP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.036	0.0692	0.2244	0.432	0.0066	0.2318	Om
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.035	0.0788	0.2684	0.32	0	0.2976	Om
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0192	0.1224	0.1888	0.3344	0.0098	0.3254	Om
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0102	0.0098	0.1038	0.3094	0.0104	0.5564	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0436	0.0836	0.2366	0.4418	0.0068	0.1876	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0288	0.0316	0.1772	0.3616	0.0072	0.3936	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.0306	0.0304	0.1222	0.2642	0.0108	0.5418	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0474	0.0388	0.194	0.322	0.0074	0.3904	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0226	0.0386	0.236	0.4348	0.0076	0.2604	Om
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0024	0.001	0.2646	0.1186	0.0788	0.5346	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0018	0.0062	0.3228	0.295	0.0144	0.3598	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0026	0.0036	0.3648	0.233	0.0166	0.3794	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0	0.0362	0.2278	0.2348	0.0382	0.4622	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0178	0.0274	0.2834	0.1914	0.0402	0.4398	SP

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0136	0.0302	0.2974	0.316	0.0084	0.3344	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0	0.0166	0.1994	0.091	0.075	0.618	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0024	0.0464	0.2456	0.1742	0.054	0.4774	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0	0.0136	0.3086	0.2266	0.0214	0.4292	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.003	0.044	0.195	0.139	0.0464	0.5726	SP

Table S42.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_l_eaf	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0384	0.2122	0.167	0.0048	0.0156	0.3348	0.1734	0.037	0.0086	0.0082	pred_gr_egll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.065	0.33	0.0928	0	0.0118	0.3258	0.159	0.0016	0.013	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.042	0.275	0.0918	0	0.0188	0.4	0.1646	0.0022	0.005	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0268	0.3134	0.0682	0.005	0.0436	0.3316	0.1656	0.018	0.0242	0.0036	pred_gr_egll
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0134	0.2224	0.003	0.003	0.012	0.5712	0.053	0.0196	0.102	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0264	0.3414	0.0824	0	0.004	0.2906	0.2442	0.0048	0.0058	0	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.021	0.3078	0.0362	0	0.0074	0.387	0.2282	0.0038	0.0078	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.1364	0.1412	0.02	0.0016	0.0154	0.2688	0.3134	0.0702	0.0324	0	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0464	0.2742	0.0396	0.0012	0.0262	0.344	0.2514	0.01	0.0064	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0456	0.312	0.0502	0.0016	0.021	0.338	0.2114	0.0028	0.0172	0	pred_gr_egll

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0076	0.0364	0	0.0766	0.0324	0.1066	0.1654	0.5032	0.0552	0.0158	pred_lg_ab
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0122	0.2678	0.0028	0.0114	0.0102	0.3234	0.2796	0.0332	0.0586	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0046	0.209	0.0018	0.0068	0.013	0.5734	0.1688	0.0108	0.0102	0.0016	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.008	0.2518	0	0.0352	0.02	0.3826	0.1464	0.0668	0.082	0.0068	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0284	0.1194	0.0216	0.0964	0.0712	0.1498	0.1526	0.2766	0.072	0.012	pred_lg_ab
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0258	0.2276	0.0248	0.002	0.0206	0.5198	0.1688	0.0052	0.005	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0	0.0894	0	0.122	0.0102	0.3502	0.104	0.1666	0.1328	0.0236	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0102	0.1858	0.0022	0.016	0.0342	0.4946	0.1404	0.0396	0.0736	0.0034	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0036	0.2082	0	0.018	0.0268	0.5342	0.1424	0.0396	0.0224	0.0044	pred_gr_egll
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0	0.1146	0.0048	0.0846	0.0274	0.426	0.1068	0.148	0.081	0.006	pred_gr_egll

Table S43.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset; shape ratio trait measurements; homologous morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0934	0.4272	0.0378	0.3904	0.0512	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.099	0.506	0.0084	0.3752	0.0114	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0666	0.4758	0.0116	0.428	0.018	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.058	0.5162	0.0504	0.3572	0.0182	Gr
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0644	0.3684	0.0812	0.4566	0.0294	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0324	0.4826	0.006	0.4702	0.0088	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0366	0.4748	0.0128	0.4688	0.007	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.1668	0.1614	0.0912	0.5662	0.0144	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0764	0.466	0.0174	0.4264	0.0138	Gr
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0572	0.4728	0.0146	0.438	0.0174	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.019	0.17	0.4544	0.323	0.0336	Lg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.024	0.4822	0.0516	0.4348	0.0074	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0362	0.4968	0.0372	0.4196	0.0102	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0224	0.4752	0.1224	0.3714	0.0086	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0388	0.2972	0.2782	0.3556	0.0302	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.063	0.4644	0.0406	0.4016	0.0304	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0114	0.4092	0.2424	0.3072	0.0298	Gr

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0294	0.462	0.1	0.397	0.0116	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0254	0.4692	0.0872	0.4104	0.0078	Gr
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0196	0.414	0.1536	0.4066	0.0062	Gr

Table S44.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset, log-shape variable measurements; functional morphology.

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	Ll	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.1734	0.0744	0.2814	0.4708	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1654	0.018	0.3412	0.4754	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1154	0.0274	0.371	0.4862	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1242	0.0908	0.3442	0.4408	Ll
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.1476	0.0512	0.3506	0.4506	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.055	0.012	0.33	0.603	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.08	0.0168	0.3772	0.526	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.2284	0.0568	0.1408	0.574	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.1228	0.038	0.3622	0.477	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.1184	0.0254	0.3564	0.4998	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.3172	0.2226	0.1234	0.3368	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1	0.0884	0.3318	0.4798	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1158	0.0856	0.366	0.4326	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1338	0.1186	0.2666	0.481	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.2274	0.1792	0.2126	0.3808	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.1154	0.0564	0.3712	0.457	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1728	0.1386	0.2284	0.4602	Ll

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.1216	0.1048	0.33	0.4436	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.1166	0.0936	0.3088	0.481	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.1326	0.1128	0.3008	0.4538	LI

Table S45.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset, log-shape variable measurements; functional morphology.

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.048	0.1128	0.1886	0.3946	0	0.256	Om
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.132	0.0242	0.4678	0.2874	0.001	0.0876	GP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.089	0.0388	0.4276	0.3064	0.001	0.1372	GP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.09	0.0678	0.4188	0.2426	0.0026	0.1782	GP
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.0176	0.017	0.1616	0.3042	0.0022	0.4974	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0878	0.0592	0.318	0.423	2.00E-04	0.1118	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0688	0.0196	0.2792	0.4124	8.00E-04	0.2192	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.037	0.0358	0.1808	0.3312	0.002	0.4132	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.1198	0.0192	0.3082	0.3652	0.001	0.1866	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0666	0.0274	0.3956	0.3476	0.0014	0.1614	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.012	0.0012	0.4136	0.1192	0.0708	0.3832	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0158	0.0018	0.5512	0.2036	0.0124	0.2152	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.02	0.001	0.6432	0.1574	0.0078	0.1706	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0088	0.0244	0.5178	0.1464	0.029	0.2736	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0942	0.0186	0.4072	0.1458	0.0346	0.2996	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0326	0.0216	0.428	0.2988	0.0028	0.2162	GP

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.009	0.0102	0.409	0.1138	0.0532	0.4048	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0114	0.0294	0.5126	0.148	0.0192	0.2794	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0094	0.0112	0.5726	0.1398	0.0168	0.2502	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0046	0.0336	0.342	0.1354	0.0408	0.4436	SP

Table S46.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset, log-shape variable measurements; functional morphology.

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_l_eaf	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0888	0.321	0.1506	6.00E-04	0.0296	0.1382	0.2322	0.03	0.0088	2.00E-04	om_grll_eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0802	0.261	0.101	0.0032	0.0124	0.2796	0.198	0.0098	0.0548	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0906	0.2436	0.1262	6.00E-04	0.017	0.1904	0.2918	0.0128	0.027	0	pred_leaf
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.048	0.2664	0.0708	0.0114	0.0268	0.2836	0.2234	0.032	0.0376	0	pred_gr_egll
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.049	0.2998	0.0296	0.0046	0.0182	0.1426	0.3026	0.0886	0.0646	4.00E-04	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.068	0.2888	0.153	0	0.0044	0.131	0.3354	0.0064	0.013	0	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0674	0.2842	0.1184	4.00E-04	0.006	0.1452	0.3466	0.0118	0.0198	2.00E-04	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.1492	0.1262	0.0452	0.0024	0.0164	0.065	0.483	0.0832	0.0292	2.00E-04	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0918	0.2704	0.1052	8.00E-04	0.0198	0.1434	0.3318	0.0182	0.0184	2.00E-04	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0832	0.2314	0.097	0.001	0.0162	0.1732	0.3564	0.0144	0.0272	0	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0166	0.0496	0.0042	0.1486	0.0178	0.0474	0.2848	0.383	0.0428	0.0052	pred_lg_ab

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.02	0.222	0.024 8	0.015	0.014	0.2062	0.3946	0.0338	0.0694	2.00E- 04	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0218	0.2072	0.023 4	0.0104	0.016 8	0.2662	0.3408	0.0362	0.0772	0	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0152	0.1692	0.019 2	0.0602	0.015 4	0.2122	0.3526	0.0756	0.0794	0.001	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0362	0.1434	0.047 4	0.1438	0.033 6	0.0942	0.2466	0.1788	0.0718	0.0042	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0664	0.223	0.080 4	0.0032	0.024	0.216	0.3364	0.0248	0.0256	2.00E- 04	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0062	0.0916	0.004 2	0.219	0.009 4	0.114	0.2782	0.1802	0.0864	0.0108	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0192	0.1936	0.02	0.0242	0.026 2	0.2316	0.3518	0.055	0.0784	0	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0156	0.1758	0.016 2	0.0238	0.020 6	0.267	0.3672	0.0548	0.058	0.001	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0134	0.1458	0.011 6	0.1266	0.015 8	0.119	0.3458	0.1424	0.0794	2.00E- 04	pred_leaf

Table S47.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset, log-shape variable measurements; functional morphology.

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

Species	Cn	Gr	Lg	Ll	Sb	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0826	0.3726	0.049	0.4512	0.0446	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0784	0.4816	0.0228	0.3806	0.0366	Gr
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0618	0.3738	0.0342	0.488	0.0422	Ll
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0442	0.4592	0.0816	0.3652	0.0498	Gr
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.058	0.4034	0.0646	0.4356	0.0384	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0356	0.4168	0.0062	0.5208	0.0206	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0402	0.378	0.017	0.538	0.0268	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.1576	0.1788	0.094	0.546	0.0236	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.07	0.3254	0.0278	0.5388	0.038	Ll
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0532	0.4182	0.0364	0.4416	0.0506	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0136	0.1222	0.4748	0.3456	0.0438	Lg
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0236	0.408	0.08	0.4736	0.0148	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0402	0.3582	0.0678	0.5082	0.0256	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0212	0.3798	0.1676	0.396	0.0354	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.037	0.1992	0.317	0.3978	0.049	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0628	0.375	0.045	0.4716	0.0456	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0142	0.3124	0.2436	0.365	0.0648	Ll
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0262	0.3586	0.142	0.4406	0.0326	Ll

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0268	0.3394	0.13	0.4684	0.0354	L1
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0186	0.3626	0.162	0.4262	0.0306	L1

Table S48.

Nesting niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset, log-shape variable measurements; homologous morphology.

Species	Ab	CR	Eg	L1	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.1662	0.0568	0.2846	0.4924	L1
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1582	0.031	0.3118	0.499	L1
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1248	0.0416	0.3102	0.5234	L1
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.1452	0.1064	0.29	0.4584	L1
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.135	0.069	0.3774	0.4186	L1
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0552	0.0238	0.317	0.604	L1
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0862	0.0284	0.3164	0.569	L1
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.2326	0.0652	0.1356	0.5666	L1
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.1406	0.0558	0.2954	0.5082	L1
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.1288	0.0486	0.3258	0.4968	L1
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.3742	0.218	0.1058	0.302	Ab
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1432	0.086	0.297	0.4738	L1
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1374	0.0982	0.3052	0.4592	L1
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.1838	0.125	0.2616	0.4296	L1
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.294	0.199	0.1668	0.3402	L1
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.1294	0.0678	0.326	0.4768	L1
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.207	0.118	0.2002	0.4748	L1
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.155	0.1198	0.2902	0.435	L1

Ecological breadth of the earliest ants

<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.1522	0.1192	0.2776	0.451	LI
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.1544	0.1236	0.2832	0.4388	LI

Table S49.

Foraging niche prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset, log-shape variable measurements; homologous morphology.

Species	Fg	Gn	GP	Om	Py	SP	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.0526	0.1876	0.1334	0.2536	0.0062	0.3666	SP
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0434	0.0884	0.237	0.4156	0.0074	0.2082	Om
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0424	0.0982	0.2884	0.3152	0.0014	0.2544	Om
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.033	0.1188	0.2166	0.317	0.009	0.3056	Om
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.022	0.0202	0.1314	0.3288	0.0114	0.4862	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0532	0.1232	0.247	0.387	0.007	0.1826	Om
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0408	0.0478	0.2056	0.3484	0.0066	0.3508	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.032	0.049	0.1414	0.2564	0.0112	0.51	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0582	0.0512	0.2278	0.324	0.0072	0.3316	SP
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0362	0.0588	0.2594	0.405	0.0076	0.233	Om
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0036	0.0042	0.324	0.1058	0.101	0.4614	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.003	0.0082	0.3546	0.2944	0.0206	0.3192	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0056	0.0062	0.4012	0.2294	0.0212	0.3364	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0026	0.0298	0.2894	0.219	0.0462	0.413	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0186	0.0334	0.3224	0.1716	0.0522	0.4018	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0236	0.0414	0.32	0.313	0.0082	0.2938	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0016	0.016	0.2758	0.1076	0.0928	0.5062	SP
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0052	0.0418	0.3006	0.164	0.0578	0.4306	SP

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<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.0016	0.013	0.3696	0.2216	0.03	0.3642	GP
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0036	0.0402	0.255	0.1484	0.0568	0.496	SP

Table S50.

Functional role prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset, log-shape variable measurements; homologous morphology.

Species	om_cn_ab	om_grll_eg	om_le_af	om_lg_ab	pred_cr	pred_gr_egll	pred_l_eaf	pred_lg_ab	pred_ll_eg	pred_s_ub	Predicted aspect
<i>Ceratomyrmex planus</i>	0.062	0.2386	0.182 2	0.0032	0.019 4	0.1806	0.2468	0.0564	0.0058	0.005	pred_leaf
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0832	0.3168	0.150 6	0.0024	0.018 2	0.159	0.2412	0.0138	0.013	0.0018	om_grll_eg
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.075	0.256	0.169 4	0.0016	0.025 8	0.1868	0.2578	0.0156	0.0102	0.0018	pred_leaf
<i>Ceratomyrmex ellenbergeri</i>	0.0556	0.2986	0.112	0.0048	0.038 2	0.1558	0.2606	0.0502	0.0188	0.0054	om_grll_eg
<i>Protoceratomyrmex revelatus</i>	0.052	0.3228	0.030 6	0.005	0.020 4	0.1462	0.2766	0.0724	0.0696	0.0044	om_grll_eg
<i>Linguamyrmex sp5</i>	0.0506	0.2688	0.176 2	4.00E-04	0.005 2	0.1628	0.324	0.0078	0.0026	0.0016	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp4</i>	0.0538	0.2644	0.128 2	0.001	0.008 6	0.1702	0.3502	0.0148	0.0072	0.0016	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex brevicornis</i>	0.1362	0.13	0.05	0.0046	0.019 8	0.066	0.469	0.0882	0.033	0.0032	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp2</i>	0.0838	0.2446	0.113 2	0.0014	0.027 8	0.154	0.3418	0.0254	0.0058	0.0022	pred_leaf
<i>Linguamyrmex sp1</i>	0.0702	0.2666	0.118 8	0.0016	0.027 2	0.1674	0.3092	0.0194	0.0174	0.0022	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp3</i>	0.0118	0.0388	0.002 8	0.1434	0.033 4	0.0326	0.2692	0.4268	0.028	0.0132	pred_lg_ab

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<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0244	0.2566	0.014	0.0154	0.013 8	0.108	0.485	0.0508	0.0304	0.0016	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.03	0.247	0.013	0.011	0.018 6	0.1454	0.4418	0.0518	0.0362	0.0052	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0214	0.2156	0.008 6	0.0574	0.025 4	0.1154	0.3776	0.111	0.0582	0.0094	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0432	0.1142	0.036 2	0.1226	0.057 8	0.0582	0.2544	0.2642	0.0384	0.0108	pred_lg_ab
<i>Haidomyrmex scimitarus</i>	0.0598	0.2394	0.092 2	0.0032	0.022 8	0.2304	0.3066	0.027	0.0156	0.003	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp5</i>	0.0064	0.095	0.007 4	0.2178	0.013 6	0.1068	0.2562	0.1764	0.0956	0.0248	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex sp4</i>	0.0276	0.2278	0.012 8	0.0218	0.035	0.1298	0.4024	0.0826	0.0536	0.0066	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex indet1</i>	0.023	0.2272	0.011	0.026	0.031 8	0.127	0.4248	0.0804	0.0408	0.008	pred_leaf
<i>Haidomyrmex indet2</i>	0.0148	0.1566	0.011	0.1254	0.027 4	0.1138	0.3098	0.1684	0.0654	0.0074	pred_leaf

Table S51.

Ecomorph prediction votes when using model trained on subset of complete morphometrics dataset, log-shape variable measurements; homologous morphology.

Lineage	Average ecological disparity	Standard deviation of ecological disparity
Ponerines (<i>Anochetus</i> and <i>Odontomachus</i>)	4.701	2.553
Dacetines (<i>Acanthognathus</i> , <i>Daceton</i> , <i>Epopostruma</i> , <i>Microdaceton</i> , and <i>Orectognathus</i>)	4.667	2.570
<i>Strumigenys</i>	3.200	1.600
<i>Myrmoteras</i>	1.333	0.471
Haidomyrmecines (conservative estimate)	2.944	1.632
Haidomyrmecines (comprehensive estimate)	3.448	1.746

Table S52.

Average and standard deviation of ecological disparity calculated as pairwise distances between each unique three-dimensional occupation. Haidomyrmecine conservative estimates are derived from only the majority aspect predicted by the raw functional measurement model, while comprehensive estimates are derived from majority aspects predicted from all four RF models.

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